

Iraq's Electoral Political Dynamics: Traditional Structures vis-à-vis Reformist Tendencies

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Iraq's parliamentary electoral system has witnessed various developments since its official establishment in 2005—2 years following the 2003 US-led invasion which toppled the former regime under Saddam Hussein's rule. Almost two decades after the first elections, whilst some customary traits remained, others faded away. One custom that remained strong is the ethnic-sectarian apportionment of powers known as al-Muhasasa al-Tai'fiyah ['Muhasasa System' hereafter] which allocates the main three presidential positions as follows: a Shia Arab for the Prime Minister's position; a Kurd for the President's position; and a Sunni Arab for the Speaker of Parliament's position (Dodge and Mansour 2020, 58). An unusual practice (amongst many others) which emerged in the new political order is the revival of reformist forces that are hostile towards the traditional and ruling Islamist political forces (Alkinani 2022). The recent existing scholarship is focused on a narrowed viewpoint towards reform being limited to opposition forces only, and overly focuses on the parliamentary electoral dynamics vis-à-vis the provincial (Eriksson and Grief 2023, 363; Berman, Clarke and Majed 2020, 27). This intervention aims to shed light on two understudied angles in the current scholarship on post-2003 Iraq's democratic and electoral system: the emergent reformist

tendencies within the political class; and the impacts of traditional parties' continued attempt to dominate power regardless of the electoral results with a focus on Iraq's latest provincial elections. The former is noticed through the public's keenness in supporting—electorally and politically—any candidates that are not affiliated with the Iran-affiliated electoral coalition known as the Coordination Framework. While the latter raises a very important point in the limitations to democratic reform and practice in post-2003 Iraq.

Reforming and Preserving the Electorate (2019-2022)

Iraq's electorate faced its most apparent existential crisis when anti-government protests known as the Tishreen [October] protest movement began in October 2019 as it challenged the status quo's Muhasasa System, which led to the system's first governmental resignations, electoral law amendments, and the early elections (O'Driscoll and Costantini 2023, 69-76). The political elite was seen as compensating for the public dissatisfaction with governmental failure in providing efficient public services and solutions to unemployment rates (France 24 2019; Al-Rahim 2019). Some of the common issues that

became apparent in the political discourse and attitude during the transformation of Iraqi politics following the Tishreen movement were criticism of Iran's proxy influence; corruption; impunity; and a preference for a civic-led and reform-oriented alternative to the ruling Islamist parties (Manfredi Firmian 2024, 5- 21).

Whilst some emerging forces from the protest movement participated in the early elections of October 2021, others decided to boycott and continue the 'incomplete civil disobedience' against the ruling class (Anderson 2022, 173-177). This divided the pro-reform forces and eventually led to the traditional parties re-emerging through the new electoral cycle despite an amendment in the electoral law. Nonetheless, it is worth highlighting that despite the schism within the protest movement and the large boycott campaign, around 40 independent candidates were elected to the parliament (Jangiz 2021; Alkinani 2021). However, despite the emergence of intra-group elitist rivalries over the political leadership of each of their Shia, Sunni, and Kurdish groups—the new emerging pro-reform forces failed to influence the new changes in the long run, and the new governmental formation followed the same Muhasasa System's style, and the electoral amendment was reversed (Alkinani 2023). Most importantly, the withdrawal of the Sadrist Movement as per the directions of its leader Muqtada al-Sadr despite winning 73 seats following the October 2021 early elections—paved the way for the Iran-aligned bloc known as the Coordination Framework to fill the 'majoritarian' gap following months of a political deadlock between the two Shia rivals (Sadrist vs. Coordination Framework) (Yuan 2022). The Sadrist withdrawal made it even more complicated for new independent lawmakers to engage with the Coordination

Framework on issues related to democratic reform, considering that the latter presented a hardcore in-group version of the current political sectarian rhetoric.

Reformist Tendencies within the Political Elite

In December 2023, Iraq's 15 provinces (excluding the Kurdistan Region's 3 provinces) held its first provincial elections in a decade (Rasheed and Azhari 2023). Iraq held its last provincial elections in April 2013, and the parliament voted to dissolve the provincial elections in response to Tishreen's pro-reform protests in 2019 which accused the councils of representing a major element of the country's state of corruption (Menmy 2023). The latest provincial elections were also faced with a low turnout due to early disappointments over reducing the number of electoral districts and recurring the Sainte Lague system of proportional representation (Menmy 2023) – reversing the previously mentioned amendments to the electoral law following Tishreen's pro-reform movement.

The Coordination Framework's gradual domination of the political arena did not end with the sudden Sadrist withdrawal from the Iraqi parliament and the entire political process. It became apparent that the Coordination Framework aimed to remove even the successful governors in the provincial elections from the scene despite the latter's sweeping victory following the latest provincial elections. Just over a month following the provincial elections, the Coordination Framework's leadership reportedly decided that they would not renew any term for any of the electorally winning governors and would reward them with positions outside the governorates' administrations. This indicated an alarming violation of the electorate and its results.

The votes of the public in the provincial elections were to elect the governors and the members of the provincial councils. The Coordination Framework is politicizing the results by appointing their prioritized candidates and transferring the candidates who won the elections towards 'other' positions (Saeed 2024). Why are the Pro-Iran blocs deteriorating the electorate at a time when it represents the parliamentary majority and under a government it formed?

Preventing Future Provincial Independent Alliances

The Coordination Framework's rationale behind preventing the electorally successful governors in the recent elections from earning their positions is interpreted as a fear of the possibility of some governors resorting to forming their alliances in the future and becoming important rivals in the upcoming parliamentary elections of 2025. The last thing the Coordination Framework wants is the emergence of new political forces, following years of being challenged and exhausted by pro-reform forces from Tishreen and the Sadrists.

Whilst the majority of the Iran-allied bloc insists on excluding the newly and repeatedly elected governors, there are still some forces within the Coordination Framework which recognizes that preventing some of the electorally winning governors comes with major challenges and may raise tensions in the street. This is particularly relevant in Basra, where its increasingly popular governor Asaad Al-Eidani, received enough votes that qualify him to re-assume the position (Menmy 2024). However, the Coordination Framework and Asaib Ahl Al-Haq in particular, categorically refuse to renew Al-Eidani's term by trying to install Uday Awwad, who

received a very small percentage of votes compared to Al-Eidani (964media 2024).

This is not the first time that political parties attempted to override election results. Iraq's previous electoral experiences witnessed the inability of Iraqi politician Iyad Allawi to become Prime Minister despite his electoral win in 2010, and the inability of the Sadrists Movement to create a parliamentary majority and form a government despite an electoral victory in 2021 (Katzman 2010, 1-8; Mansour and Robin-D'Cruz 2022, 2-4). These past experiences reminisce with the victory of the provincial governors of Basra, Karbala, and Wasit, who were not able to form their local governments. This will lead Iraqis to lose confidence in the feasibility of the elections—that is if they did not lose it. Some of the electorally winning governors were faced with intimidation and threats by traditional political parties.

The Coordination Framework's hostility towards the three governors in Karbala, Basra, and Wasit is interpreted due to the candidates not running on the framework's list and decided to nominate separately considering their great popularity in their governorates. This reflects the Coordination Framework's early cautiousness towards allowing any candidates to emerge beyond the framework's influence and indicates a politicized pressure towards the electorate, hence undermining the democratic nature. Moreover, the Pro-Iran bloc would most likely find ways to create divisions within the coalitions of the winning candidates to undermine the latter's internal legitimacies in front of the public opinion—a common tactic in Iraqi electoral politics.

Conclusion

Reform in Iraq is no longer limited to the

interests of the Tishreen protest movement and its affiliated emerging parties, activists, and supporters. As previously discussed, the lead-up to the parliamentary elections signaled a major division between the protest movement's candidates—independent lawmakers—and the established political parties over amending versus maintaining the status-quo. The political deadlock that overshadowed the governmental formation and led to a delay of around one year since the elections took place indicated that the 'reform' debate is amongst the establishment's political parties.

This intra-elitist schism over encouraging or limiting reform was reflected following the December 2023 provincial elections. This reassures that despite pessimism in the Iraqi political structure, recent development indicates that while there are limitations to reform in both the system and elections—there is still an evident reflection of willingness towards "new" faces—both Tishreeni and emerging independent figures—challenging the traditional status-quo. Reform in post-2003 Iraq has reconstructed into becoming a focus debated across different political forces, beyond the protest movement, including the establishment's elite. ♦

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